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*THE EVOLUTION OF FEMALE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN BRAZIL*¹

A EVOLUÇÃO DO EMPREENDEDORISMO FEMININO NO BRASIL

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ABSTRACT

This is a bibliographical research that reflects on the evolution of female entrepreneurship in Brazil, through a survey carried out in Brazilian scientific journals. It sought to systematically review the body of work already produced on the subject, retracing the steps taken in a way that encourages the systematization, organization, and democratization of access to scientific research. As a result, data were presented on academic production, analyzing the volume of articles on this subject, the topics investigated, the methodological process, and the characteristics and particularities of women entrepreneurs.

Keywords: female entrepreneurship, bibliographic research, state of the art.

RESUMO

Trata-se de uma pesquisa bibliográfica que reflete sobre a evolução do empreendedorismo feminino no Brasil, através de levantamento realizado em revistas científicas brasileiras. Buscou realizar um balanço sistemático da produção já realizada sobre a temática, revendo o caminho percorrido, de modo que favorece a sistematização, a organização e a democratização ao acesso às pesquisas científicas. Como resultado apresentou dados sobre a produção acadêmica, analisando o volume dos artigos com esta temática, as temáticas investigadas, processo metodológico e características e particularidades das mulheres empreendedoras.

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Palavras-Chave: empreendedorismo feminino, pesquisa bibliográfica, estado da arte.

INTRODUCTION

This research addresses aspects of female entrepreneurship. Female entrepreneurship has been gaining increasing prominence in the job market, which has sparked interest in the public sector and, consequently, in academia regarding the attempt to identify the motivations behind this phenomenon (Alperstedt et al., 2014).

Female entrepreneurship has been strengthening with the changes in the labor market and in families (Silva et al., 2016). Previously, women entered the workforce mainly during times of crisis, taking on a secondary role and being seen as occasional, precarious labor to meet their families' financial needs, since the main or sole provider could not do so (Abramo, 2007).

Today, women have established their place in the job market and often choose entrepreneurship when faced with the hostility of the workforce, which hinders their career growth. In addition, the need to reconcile family and work, as well as the desire for financial independence in order to escape abusive and violent situations at home in some cases, also motivates this choice (Silva; Krakauer, 2023).

Several studies show that women are motivated to undertake entrepreneurship for the following reasons: financial independence, personal fulfillment, and the search for balance between family and work (Castro; Braz; Freitas, 2019; Bandeira; Amorim; Oliveira, 2020; Pinheiros; Dias, 2020).

Given this context and the theme addressed here, which focuses on women entrepreneurs, this work is a qualitative study characterized by bibliographic exploration to present the state of the art regarding studies on women entrepreneurs. According to Silva et al. (2020), this type of research seeks to carry out a systematic review of the existing literature on the topic,

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retracing the path taken in a way that facilitates the systematization, organization, and democratization of access to scientific research.

The search was carried out in Brazilian journals with Qualis (qualification) A3, B1, B2, and B3, using the following keywords: entrepreneurship, female entrepreneurship, and women's entrepreneurial motivation. These terms were chosen after a general survey identified them as the most commonly used for the study presented.

Thus, this article seeks to present an overview that, besides systematically organizing the studies on the topic from 2019 to 2024, can answer the following question: What has been studied in Brazilian journals about female entrepreneurship? In this way, objectives were outlined, with the general objective of studying the evolution of Brazilian female entrepreneurship from 2019 to 2024. The specific objectives are: (i) to verify the approach of studies on female entrepreneurship; and (ii) to analyze the volume of research on the presented topic.

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

Entrepreneurship and female entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship is a driving force in the economy, and it is impossible to think about economic development without considering the role of entrepreneurial leaders, who identify social or technological changes and transform them into opportunities for the development of new businesses (Baggio; Baggio, 2014).

This is because entrepreneurship involves engaging people in the process of transforming ideas into opportunities and implementing these ideas as businesses (Sentanin; Barboza, 2005).

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Entrepreneurship can be seen as the ability to turn ideas into reality, driven by creativity and motivation. It involves the satisfaction of achieving goals, bringing together efforts and innovations in any personal or professional endeavor, continually facing challenges and opportunities, and acting proactively to solve issues (Sentanin; Barboza, 2005).

Entrepreneurship represents the discovery of an individual's full potential, both rational and intuitive. It is a journey of self-reflection, continuous learning, and openness to new experiences and innovative concepts (Baggio; Baggio, 2014).

However, every definition of entrepreneurship includes, at a minimum, the following elements related to the entrepreneur: 1) initiative in founding a new venture and passion for the work; 2) innovative use of available resources, altering the surrounding social and economic context; 3) willingness to take calculated risks and face the possibility of failure (Baggio; Baggio, 2014).

Although these characteristics are considered important for defining entrepreneurship, it has been observed that women naturally display greater sensitivity, empathy, commitment, and a desire to help. These qualities contribute to women's success as entrepreneurs, especially in the service sector. These traits are advantageous in this field because they facilitate the necessary interactions with clients, collaborators, and communities, enabling differentiated and innovative development (Amorim; Batista, 2012).

In recent years, women's involvement in entrepreneurship has been growing, resulting from several changes in family structures and the labor market (Silva et al., 2016). Family and labor market values have changed, and women began to work to support men in providing for the household. As a result of this shift, the number of women entrepreneurs has increased (Silva et al., 2016). Previously, society used biological arguments to justify inequalities between men

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and women, but over time, it has become clear that the differences between the two are rooted in diverse skills (Amorim; Batista, 2012).

Initially, women were considered less capable of working outside the home, as reflected in the old saying that “a woman's place is at home.” However, this is now recognized as a historical and social construct leading to women’s entry into entrepreneurship (Amorim; Batista, 2012).

With the Industrial Revolution, the number of women working in factories increased because there was a need to boost productivity. Another significant entry of women into the labor market occurred in the twentieth century during the First and Second World Wars, as the high number of deaths during these conflicts made it essential to hire women for positions previously reserved for men (Sentanin; Barboza, 2005).

From these periods onward, women began organizing themselves into associations, organizations, and unions to fight for better working conditions, equal pay, and recognition. However, although they were recruited for jobs previously held only by men, there remained a stark wage gap. In response to these factors, women began seeking entrepreneurship - not only for multiple reasons, but also with the pursuit of recognition and higher income among their motivations.

Women's entrepreneurial motivation

Motivation can be directly related to values, expectations, needs, or feelings, driving an individual to act to achieve a particular goal. In the literature, entrepreneurial motivation is categorized as either necessity-based or opportunity-based. Motivation by necessity is usually linked to dissatisfaction with one’s job or a perceived lack of opportunities in the labor market. Opportunity-based motivation is related to the entrepreneur’s perception of a problem that can be solved (Bandeira; Amorim; Oliveira, 2020; Silva; Oliveira, 2023).

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When the decision to undertake entrepreneurship is motivated by opportunity, the main drivers are the desire for autonomy and the identification of a business opportunity (Castro; Braz; Freitas, 2019; Bandeira; Amorim; Oliveira, 2020).

In their research, Bandeira, Amorim, and Oliveira (2020) found that motivations for entrepreneurship and the factors guiding career decisions cannot be attributed solely to gender. Variables such as professional background, personal characteristics, and the context in which the individual is situated must be analyzed. The study's results showed that when starting their businesses, women's motivations were not limited to financial aspirations, unlike men. Women highlighted motivations such as personal values, the pursuit of balance between family and work, and the freedom to choose how to work. In contrast, men indicated motivations such as identifying a business opportunity, earning supplementary income, and increasing financial gain.

Pinheiro and Dias (2020) found, in the initial phase of their research, that women's motivations for entrepreneurship were diverse, including social responsibility, being laid off, personal fulfillment, market needs, and the desire to contribute to activities already developed by their husbands. A more detailed analysis of the results revealed that all interviewees unanimously cited financial independence and personal fulfillment as reasons for pursuing entrepreneurship.

In a study of Black women, it was found that the motivating factors for starting businesses were structural sexism and racism, as these women did not see the possibility of advancing in the companies where they worked due to being both women and Black. When asked about the advantages of entrepreneurship, interviewees agreed that it provided time freedom and the opportunity to choose their professional and personal decisions. Among the disadvantages, they mentioned excessive work, financial instability, and lack of time (Silva; Krakauer, 2023).

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Challenges faced by women entrepreneurs

Women face, in addition to the intrinsic challenges of entrepreneurship, difficulties stemming from a sexist and patriarchal society, such as social, cultural, and economic barriers (Castro; Braz; Freitas, 2019; Silva; Krakauer, 2023).

Women's challenges in the labor market date back to colonial Brazil, when the dominant class expected women to act as mothers and wives, staying indoors with children, family, and household staff. At every stage of life, women were in a position of absolute dependency in their roles - first as daughters, then as mothers and wives - always serving the household as needed. This patriarchal regime differentiates the sexes, with women restricted to childcare, domestic responsibilities, and subordination to husbands, while men had various opportunities (Pineiro; Dias, 2020).

At that time, women were only integrated into the labor market during economic crises, considered a secondary labor force to help supplement family income when the husband - the main or sole breadwinner - was unemployed or had reduced income or had died. Women's participation was viewed as secondary, precarious, unstable, and temporary, as they would leave work and return to domestic roles once the husband was employed or earning more (Abramo, 2007).

Since the 1950s, women have moved beyond secondary roles and established their place in the labor market, actively pursuing their professional careers while continuing to manage household responsibilities - a double burden (Pineiro; Dias, 2020).

Some women choose entrepreneurship due to difficulties advancing in the labor market, workplace hostility, the need to balance family and work, and the desire for financial independence to escape abusive or violent living conditions (Silva; Krakauer, 2023).

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One of the motivating factors for entrepreneurship is the ability to balance work and family. According to Goldenberg (2023), women perform the invisible, unpaid work of caring for children, home, and family for an average of 4 hours and 25 minutes per day. Women are overwhelmed by this invisible labor, which impacts their career plans and professional performance. The paternalistic and sexist society considers men as secondary actors in invisible tasks - participating only occasionally - while women are seen as the main protagonists.

A study with female entrepreneurs in Curitiba showed that the choice of entrepreneurship was based on both social and economic factors. On the social side, cultural aspects of a patriarchal society assign women roles of submission and obedience to men, so women's struggle is for rights related to freedom and equality. Economically, entrepreneurship represents financial emancipation, as women take on the role of provider and find satisfaction. The study observed that starting a business is a significant challenge for women, as they must prove their ability to manage, which is part of the ongoing fight for space, voice, and equality (Morais; Krupczak; Garcia, 2023).

Silva, Mainardes, and Lasso (2016) studied a group of women entrepreneurs and former women business owners. When asked about the main difficulties faced in their ventures, they cited: obtaining bank loans, business expansion, lack of market recognition, fierce competition, administrative issues, high tax burdens, customer acquisition, fear of failure, and lack of family support. The interviewees who were no longer in business cited reasons such as the inability to grow their ventures or the high workload that made it impossible to manage household, family, and self-care.

Ferreira, Bastos, and D'Ángelo (2018) studied the transition process of women from formal employment to entrepreneurship. The interviewees reported no problems in management positions due to being women and felt satisfied in their work relationships. However, they faced restrictions in career progression

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because women had breaks and interruptions, while men had more linear careers. These interruptions were seen as natural by the interviewees and did not cause frustration, as most did not have a defined career plan before becoming mothers - they sought stable jobs with attractive pay and growth opportunities. After having children, interviewees reevaluated their careers due to frustrations and chose entrepreneurship mainly for professional fulfillment and greater flexibility in balancing work and family. In contrast to other studies that highlighted the lack of family support, this research found that all the interviewees were married, and partners played a key role in providing psychological and/or financial support for them to start their businesses.

Vieira et al. (2022) studied a group of women entrepreneurs participating in the Women Entrepreneurs Research Project at the University of Brasília and identified their main difficulties and challenges. Most interviewees reported experiencing prejudice, being compared to men, disbelief in their business, devaluation, criticism, and being deemed less credible because they were women. When asked about management challenges, the women cited difficulty finding qualified labor, competition, monetization, administrative issues, and difficulty obtaining credit. Regarding resources, the main challenges were lack of experience in applying initial resources, as well as difficulties in obtaining financial and social capital.

In Brazil, to support female entrepreneurship, the Federal Government created the microcredit program “Crescer,” aimed at providing credit to small business owners, with a focus on women. Facilitating access to credit gives women initial capital to start or expand their businesses. However, to address women's needs in management, it is essential that microcredit programs be complemented by business management and financial education training (Marques et al., 2024). In the study by Silva, Mainardes, and Lasso (2016), it was noted that entrepreneurs only sought bank loans as a last resort, since 14% of

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the respondents, after three years of running their businesses, continued to use their own financial resources.

METHODOLOGICAL PROCEDURES

This work is characterized as exploratory and qualitative, as it explores the literature to present the state of the art on studies related to women entrepreneurs. According to Silva et al. (2020), this type of research seeks to conduct a systematic review of the existing literature, revisiting the path taken, in order to facilitate the systematization, organization, and democratization of access to scientific research. The search was conducted in journals with Qualis (qualification) A3, B1, B2, and B3, using the following keywords, chosen after a general search in the Google Scholar repository: female entrepreneurship and women entrepreneurs. These terms are the most frequent in articles related to the theme.

Thus, this work studies the evolution of female entrepreneurship, systematically organizing studies on the topic during the period from 2019 to 2024, in order to answer the following question: How is female entrepreneurship being studied in Brazilian journals between 2019 and 2024?

The time frame was chosen because the rates of early-stage and established female entrepreneurship were high in 2019, and in the following years, GEM/DATA SEBRAE data classified by gender showed a decrease in these rates. Therefore, the aim is to understand whether academic production in this period reflects the events that occurred in society.

A methodological cut was also made by searching only in journals classified as A3, B1, B2, and B3, which portray the reality of Brazilian academic research in national journals.

The data collection and analysis procedure took place according to the following steps: i) a general search for articles addressing the theme of female

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entrepreneurship in the Google Scholar repository to determine the search keywords; ii) Identification of the most cited keywords in articles related to the topic: female entrepreneurship and women entrepreneurs; iii) on the SUCUPIRA/CAPES platform, a survey was conducted to identify journals that address the theme of entrepreneurship; iv) among the Brazilian journals classified according to the research criteria, articles containing the above-mentioned keywords were selected; v) the items outlined in the objectives of this article were then analyzed, namely, publication volume, investigated topics, methodological approaches of the studies, and data collection instruments, in addition to the characteristics and particularities presented in each analyzed article.

RESULTS

A total of 23 articles were selected and analyzed in the selected journals, using the keywords female entrepreneurship and women entrepreneurs.

The survey conducted on the CAPES Sucupira Platform regarding the journals revealed the following results: one journal classified as A3 and four B2-type journals, namely: Revista de Empreendedorismo e Gestão de Pequenas Empresas (REGPEPE); Empreendedorismo, Gestão e Negócios Revista do Curso de Administração (FATECE); Revista De Empreendedorismo, Inovação e Tecnologia; Revista de Micro e Pequenas Empresas e Empreendedorismo da Fatec Osasco (REMIPE); e Revista Livre de Sustentabilidade e Empreendedorismo (RELISE).

For article selection, the period from January 2019 to July 2024 was adopted as a reference; however, it is important to highlight that the year 2024 was not fully included in the research since data collection was concluded in August.

Regarding the methodological approach used in the studies, qualitative research stands out, identified in 19 articles, and four articles used the

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quantitative method. It is noteworthy that 17.39% of the studies applied statistical and mathematical laws to understand aspects of female entrepreneurship (Table 1).

As for the types of instruments used in the studies, it was observed that 61.90% of the articles used interviews only, 14.29% applied interviews, observation, and document analysis, 9.52% used secondary data, 9.52% conducted literature reviews, and 4.76% conducted in-depth interviews (Chart 1).

Table 1: This table presents the journals, their respective Qualis classifications, methodologies, and research instruments used in each of the analyzed studies.

REVISTA	QUALIS	ARTIGO	ANO	METODOLOGIA	INSTRUMENTO
REGEPE	A3	DESENVOLVIMENTO DE UMA INOVAÇÃO DE PROCESSO EM UM EMPREENDIMENTO INFORMAL DE ARRANJOS FLORAIS	2022	Qualitativa	<i>Entrevista, Observação e Pesquisa Documental</i>
REGEPE	A3	COMPORTAMENTO EMPREENDEDOR E ESTRATÉGIA: UMA REVISÃO SISTEMÁTICA DA LITERATURA	2023	Qualitativa	Revisão da Literatura
REGEPE	A3	LIBERTEES PROJECT: ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL INSERTION FOR WOMEN DEPRIVED OF THEIR LIBERTY	2023	Qualitativa	<i>Entrevista, Observação e Pesquisa Documental</i>
REGEPE	A3	A RELAÇÃO ENTRE AS POLÍTICAS DE GÊNERO E A CRIAÇÃO DE EMPRESAS POR MULHERES	2023	Quantitativo	Dados Secundários
FATECE	B2	EMPREENDEDORISMO FEMININO: UM ESTUDO DE CASO REALIZADO NA CÂMARA DA MULHER EMPREENDEDORA DE VIÇOSA-MG	2019	Qualitativa	Entrevista
FATECE	B2	EMPREENDEDORISMO FEMININO: ESTUDO NA CÂMARA DAS MULHERES EMPRESÁRIA DA ASSOCIAÇÃO EMPRESARIAL DE CRICIÚMA	2020	Qualitativa	Entrevista
REMIPE	B2	COMPORTAMENTO EMPREENDEDOR FEMININO: ESTUDO NO ESTADO DO RIO GRANDE DO SUL	2019	Quantitativo	Entrevista
REMIPE	B2	O EMPREENDEDORISMO FEMININO NO POLO CERÂMICO DE TERESINA/PI	2022	Qualitativa	Entrevista
REMIPE	B2	COMPETÊNCIAS EMPREENDEDORAS EM MULHERES QUE ATUAM NA ECONOMIA INFORMAL BRASILEIRA	2024	Qualitativa	Entrevista
REMIPE	B2	EMPREENDEDORISMO FEMININO NA FRONTEIRA ENTRE O BRASIL E O URUGUAI: OPORTUNIDADE OU NECESSIDADE	2024	Qualitativa	Entrevista
REMIPE	B2	EMPREENDEDORISMO FEMININO: REDES DE APOIO SOCIAL PARA ATENUAR OS CONFLITOS TRABALHO-FAMÍLIA	2024	Qualitativa	Entrevista
RELISE	B2	PROJETOS SOCIAIS DE PROFISSIONALIZAÇÃO DA MULHER EMPREENDEDORA: UM ESTUDO NO CONFEITA+ LIMEIRA	2019	Qualitativa	<i>Entrevista, Observação e Pesquisa Documental</i>
RELISE	B2	DO PODER DESMISTIFICADOR DA NARRATIVA BIOGRÁFICA: O EMPREENDEDORISMO FEMININO PARA LÁ DA RETÓRICA	2019	Qualitativa	Entrevista em profundidade
RELISE	B2	EMPREENDEDORISMO FEMININO: PERFIL, DESAFIOS E CONQUISTAS NO SERTÃO CENTRAL CEARENSE	2019	Qualitativa	Entrevista
RELISE	B2	EMPREENDEDORISMO FEMININO NA PRODUÇÃO RURAL: UM ESTUDO NO OESTE CATARINENSE	2019	Qualitativa	Entrevista
RELISE	B2	MOTIVAÇÕES PARA EMPREENDER: UM ESTUDO COM MULHERES EMPREENDEDORAS	2020	Qualitativa	Entrevista
RELISE	B2	EMPREENDEDORISMO FEMININO	2021	Quantitativo	Revisão da Literatura
RELISE	B2	VIDA PESSOAL E VIDA PROFISSIONAL: UM DESAFIO PARA MULHERES EMPREENDEDORAS	2021	Qualitativa	Entrevista
RELISE	B2	EMPREENDEDORISMO FEMININO E OS DESAFIOS PERCEBIDOS POR EMPREENDEDORAS DA GERAÇÃO Y DE CAXIAS DO SUL	2022	Qualitativa	Entrevista
RELISE	B2	ANÁLISE DA PERSISTÊNCIA NO PERFIL COMPORTAMENTAL DE EMPREENDEDORAS BRASILEIRAS	2022	Qualitativa	Dados Secundários
RELISE	B2	LUZ NA PASSARELA QUE LÁ VEM ELAS: AS EMPREENDEDORAS DO E-COMMERCE DE MODA E ACESSÓRIOS	2023	Qualitativa	Entrevista

Still addressing the first objective of this study, Table 2 shows the number of articles by keyword and year found in each journal. However, it is noteworthy

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that the journals analyzed here did not present, in their databases, articles with the keywords female entrepreneurship and women entrepreneurs within the previously established period.

Chart 2: Number of journals published per year and keyword.

PALAVRA-CHAVE	REVISTA	ANO	Nº DE ARTIGOS
	RELISE	2019	1
MULHERES EMPREENDEDORAS	RELISE	2021	2
	REMIPE	2019	1
	REGEPE	2023	2
	FATECE	2019-2024	0
	FATECE	2019	1
	FATECE	2020	1
	REGEPE	2022	1
	REGEPE	2023	1
	REMIPE	2019	1
EMPREENDEDORISMO	REMIPE	2022	1
FEMININO	REMIPE	2024	2
	RELISE	2019	3
	RELISE	2020	1
	RELISE	2021	1
	RELISE	2022	2
	RELISE	2023	1

Twenty-one works addressing the theme of female entrepreneurship and women entrepreneurs were identified, with these keywords appearing either in the title or in the keywords of the publication. Of these 21 works, 10 were published in the RELISE journal; five articles in REMIPE, four studies in REGEPE, two papers in FATECE, and no articles in the Revista de Empreendedorismo, Inovação e Tecnologia, whose last publication was in 2017.

In line with the second objective of this research, it is noted that the selected articles discuss five common topics: female entrepreneurship, business innovation, entrepreneurial behavior and strategy, impact and/or social inclusion businesses, and entrepreneurial motivation. In the analysis of the theme of female entrepreneurship, six studies were found; one article on business

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innovation; eight works mentioned the topic of entrepreneurial behavior; five studies addressed entrepreneurial motivation; and two works focused on impact/social inclusion businesses (Chart 3).

Chart 3: Scientific articles divided by themes

Tema Comum	Periódico	Ano	Artigo	Autores
EMPREENDEDORISMO FEMININO	FATECE	2019	EMPREENDEDORISMO FEMININO: UM ESTUDO DE CASO REALIZADO NA CÂMARA DA MULHER EMPREENDEDORA DE VIÇOSA-MG	Castro, Braz e Freitas
	FATECE	2020	EMPREENDEDORISMO FEMININO: ESTUDO NA CÂMARA DAS MULHERES EMPRESÁRIA DA ASSOCIAÇÃO EMPRESARIAL DE CRICIÚMA	Dias e Pinheiro
	REGEPE	2023	A RELAÇÃO ENTRE AS POLÍTICAS DE GÊNERO E A CRIAÇÃO DE EMPRESAS POR MULHERES	Teixeira, Junior e Almeida
	RELISE	2019	DO PODER DESMISTIFICADOR DA NARRATIVA BIOGRÁFICA: O EMPREENDEDORISMO FEMININO PARA LÁ DA RETÓRICA	Nogueira
	RELISE	2021	EMPREENDEDORISMO FEMININO	Teixeira, <i>et al.</i>
	RELISE	2022	EMPREENDEDORISMO FEMININO E OS DESAFIOS PERCEBIDOS POR EMPREENDEDORAS DA GERAÇÃO Y DE CAXIAS DO SUL	Richter, <i>et al.</i>
NEGÓCIO DE IMPACTO SOCIAL OU INSERÇÃO SOCIAL	REGEPE	2023	LIBERTEEES PROJECT: ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL INSERTION FOR WOMEN DEPRIVED OF THEIR LIBERTY	Rio <i>et al.</i>
	RELISE	2019	PROJETOS SOCIAIS DE PROFISSIONALIZAÇÃO DA MULHER EMPREENDEDORA: UM ESTUDO NO CONFEITA+ LIMEIRA	Cruz <i>et al.</i>
INOVAÇÃO EM NEGÓCIOS	REGEPE	2022	DESENVOLVIMENTO DE UMA INOVAÇÃO DE PROCESSO EM UM EMPREENDIMENTO INFORMAL DE ARRANJOS FLORAIS	Martarello e Ferro
COMPORTAMENTO EMPREENDEDOR E ESTRATÉGIA	REGEPE	2023	COMPORTAMENTO EMPREENDEDOR E ESTRATÉGIA: UMA REVISÃO SISTEMÁTICA DA LITERATURA	Bezerra <i>et al.</i>
	REMIPE	2019	COMPORTAMENTO EMPREENDEDOR FEMININO: ESTUDO NO ESTADO DO RIO GRANDE DO SUL	Matte <i>et al.</i>
	REMIPE	2024	EMPREENDEDORISMO FEMININO NA FRONTEIRA ENTRE O BRASIL E O URUGUAI: OPORTUNIDADE OU NECESSIDADE?	Rodrigues <i>et al.</i>
	RELISE	2019	EMPREENDEDORISMO FEMININO: PERFIL, DESAFIOS E CONQUISTAS NO SERTÃO CENTRAL CEARENSE	Barbosa <i>et al.</i>
	RELISE	2019	EMPREENDEDORISMO FEMININO NA PRODUÇÃO RURAL: UM ESTUDO NO OESTE CATARINENS	Maia <i>et al.</i>
	RELISE	2021	VIDA PESSOAL E VIDA PROFISSIONAL: UM DESAFIO PARA MULHERES EMPREENDEDORAS	Senff <i>et al.</i>
	RELISE	2022	ANÁLISE DA PERSISTÊNCIA NO PERFIL COMPORTAMENTAL DE EMPREENDEDORAS BRASILEIRAS	Ferreira <i>et al.</i>
	REMIPE	2024	COMPETÊNCIAS EMPREENDEDORAS EM MULHERES QUE ATUAM NA ECONOMIA INFORMAL BRASILEIRA	Soares <i>et al.</i>
MOTIVAÇÃO EMPREENDEDORA	REMIPE	2022	O EMPREENDEDORISMO FEMININO NO POLO CERÂMICO DE TERESINA/PI	Coutinho <i>et al.</i>
	REMIPE	2024	EMPREENDEDORISMO FEMININO: REDES DE APOIO SOCIAL PARA ATENUAR OS CONFLITOS TRABALHO-FAMÍLIA	Souza <i>et al.</i>
	RELISE	2020	MOTIVAÇÕES PARA EMPREENDER: UM ESTUDO COM MULHERES EMPREENDEDORAS	Silva <i>et al.</i>
	RELISE	2023	LUZ NA PASSARELA QUE LÁ VEM ELAS: AS EMPREENDEDORAS DO E COMMERCE DE MODA E ACESSÓRIOS	Santos <i>et al.</i>
	RELISE	2021	MULHERES EMPREENDEDORAS, GRAU DE EDUCAÇÃO E ACEITAÇÃO SOCIAL DE EMPREENDEDORES: UM ESTUDO QUANTITATIVO TRANSNACIONAL	Costa <i>et al.</i>

The FATECE journal presented two studies, one in 2019 and the other in 2020, which addressed the theme of female entrepreneurship with case studies in the chambers of women entrepreneurs from the cities of Criciúma and Viçosa. Castro, Braz, and Freitas (2019) conducted a case study through interviews and observation of 10 women attending the Chamber of Women Entrepreneurs of Viçosa, identifying their sociodemographic profile and main challenges faced.

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Regarding sociodemographics, 80% of the women are between 31 and 40 years old, 60% are married, and 50% have children. As for education, 50% hold postgraduate degrees, confirming the high educational level commonly found among women entrepreneurs. The nature of their businesses is related to traditionally feminine areas, such as restaurants, acupuncture and homeopathy offices, professional training consultancies, human resources consulting, beauty salons, clinical analysis laboratories, clothing stores, aesthetic franchises, and music production.

Among the challenges faced, 50% of women pointed to the need to reconcile personal and professional life, 30% reported experiencing gender bias, along with other challenges such as lack of family support, attracting clients, competition, economic crisis, taxes, and insufficient training in administrative areas. The alliances formed through the chamber have brought benefits to the interviewees such as business promotion, the creation of partnerships, and networking.

Pinheiro and Dias (2020) also interviewed three women from the Chamber of Businesswomen of Criciúma to analyze entrepreneurial characteristics in relation to the sexual division of labor and to understand the challenges in choosing entrepreneurship.

The interviewees reported that their choice to become entrepreneurs was motivated by a common objective: to contribute financially at home, as much of their income is allocated to household expenses, but also by personal fulfillment, social responsibility, and the need to take over a family business. Challenges mentioned included taxes, the economic situation, lack of time for family due to multiple roles, marital separation, not having children or having them later in life, their field of activity, and the need to seek further knowledge. As for entrepreneurial characteristics, all described themselves as persistent; two mentioned a social vision, calculated risk-taking, leadership, and persuasion. It

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was noted that these women possess strong leadership traits, empowerment, and active participation in social actions that foster women's empowerment.

Articulating entrepreneurial characteristics with the sexual division of labor, it was observed that gender inequality persists and that women, while entering the public sphere, are also obliged to continue caring for the private sphere and must manage activities in both realms, often needing to dedicate themselves more than men to prove their competence.

Two articles from Regepe addressed female entrepreneurship, one in 2022 focusing on innovation and the other in 2023 on entrepreneurial behavior. Martarello and Ferro (2022) conducted interviews, observation, and documentary research in an unregistered floral arrangements business to understand the facts and experiences leading to the creation and maintenance of the business. The entrepreneur was motivated by the pursuit of financial independence and personal fulfillment. The business lacked technological capabilities, which required an innovative solution since productivity was hindered by a specific operation—removing thorns and leaves. This prompted the development of a mechanized rose extractor, which improved the creation of floral arrangements and sped up the florist's work, bringing differentiation to the business. The use of this machine resulted in greater productive efficiency, safety, hygiene, and cost and time reduction. The main social contribution of this article is to highlight improvements for businesses belonging to socially disadvantaged groups, in this case, women.

On entrepreneurial behavior, Bezerra et al. (2023) highlight the importance of understanding how the intersection between entrepreneurial behavior and strategy can be a competitive differentiator for business growth. They point out that characteristics related to feminine values, such as altruism, sensitivity, courage, continuous learning, openness to innovation, and

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interpersonal relationships, influence the strategies adopted by women in their businesses, in customer relations, marketing, and crisis response.

A search for the keyword “women entrepreneurs” yielded two articles in 2023, one addressing female entrepreneurship and the other social impact/social inclusion businesses, as shown in Chart 3 above.

Rios et al. (2023) studied a project called Liberteas, where women entrepreneurs used innovation to transform challenges into opportunities, as in Bezerra et al. (2023). This project, however, brought a positive social impact to women deprived of their freedom, even during the pandemic, which imposed multiple challenges, including financial limitations, declining sales, and social isolation. The entrepreneurs demonstrated resilience and adaptability in keeping the business economically sustainable while generating social impact. The project empowered women in prison by providing training, self-esteem, financial independence, and sentence reduction. It was noted that these entrepreneurs developed support networks and significant partnerships to take part in acceleration programs and maintain business sustainability, even in the face of patriarchal prejudice.

This study corroborates Bezerra et al. (2023) by illustrating the importance of the intersection between entrepreneurial behavior and strategic choices for women to keep businesses sustainable and impactful, despite numerous challenges that could make the business unfeasible.

Teixeira et al. (2023) examined the effects of gender policies on women’s business creation through secondary data on the legal nature of women-owned businesses (Limited Business Company [LTDA] and Individual Limited Liability Company [EIRELI]) from the Municipal Basic Information Survey (MUNIC) and public CNPJ data from the Federal Revenue Service. The study emphasized the importance of considering the specificities of each group of women when creating public policies so that they are tailored to each group’s reality. The authors

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showed that gender policies are fundamental to women's business creation, as some difficulties—like gender discrimination, bureaucracy, lack of recognition, and scarce resources—are more acute for women who undertake alone, but not as much for those in partnerships. Policies to combat sexual discrimination and promote access to education, well-being, and health can help women stay in business, generating more equality for those who still face social judgment, scarce resources, and the double burden of private and public life, as also mentioned by Castro, Braz, and Freitas (2019).

The studies on the themes established by the research show that the REMIPE journal published work by Matte et al. (2019), which found that Brazilian women were responsible for nearly 50% of new businesses established in 2017. The research examined the peculiarities of entrepreneurial behavior among women in municipalities in Rio Grande do Sul. Drawing on the work of psychologist David McClelland, the study analyzed sociodemographic factors and the reasons that lead women to start or sustain their businesses. Using a quantitative approach and the "Behavioral Diagnosis" questionnaire from SEBRAE's Business-to-Business Project, 711 businesswomen in the state were surveyed. Results revealed that these entrepreneurs are characterized by a relentless pursuit of challenging goals, continuous improvement, and a striving for excellence, always aiming for recognition of their results.

In 2021 and 2022, the journal did not publish any work on female entrepreneurship or women entrepreneurs with these keywords in the title or list of keywords.

The study by Coutinho et al. (2022) explored the role of female entrepreneurship in the ceramics hub of Teresina, Piauí, amid the growth of female-owned businesses. The study investigated motivations, future expectations, and challenges faced by women in their professional journeys. Qualitative methodologies were used, including interviews and questionnaires to

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clarify socioeconomic profiles. Eight entrepreneurs were selected for the research, chosen for accessibility from a total of 14 businesswomen. Results showed that necessity-driven entrepreneurship prevails in this context. The main obstacle cited was balancing professional and family responsibilities. The research also found that age influences expectations: older entrepreneurs are less likely to consider change, while younger ones are more optimistic about the future of their businesses. Despite challenges, participants felt satisfied with their professional paths.

In 2023, the journal again did not publish any work on female entrepreneurship or women entrepreneurs with relevant titles or keywords, as in 2021 and 2022.

Soares et al. (2024) conducted a study aimed at identifying the main entrepreneurial skills among women operating in the informal economy in Brazil. This qualitative research conducted semi-structured interviews based on the competency model proposed by Man and Lau (2000). The analysis revealed competencies such as environmental awareness, valuing networks, and the ability to form partnerships. The work provides a theoretical contribution by exploring the particular entrepreneurial skills of this group and highlights the professional maturity of these women, challenging the idea that informal businesses are poorly professionalized. The results emphasize the importance of these competencies for the success and sustainability of businesses in such a challenging environment.

Rodrigues et al. (2024) sought to understand the factors that drive women in Santana do Livramento, Brazil, and Rivera, Uruguay, to become entrepreneurs, as well as the main challenges they face and whether entrepreneurship is driven by opportunity or necessity. Using a qualitative and descriptive approach, the study employed the narrative method and conducted semi-structured interviews with 22 women, equally distributed between the two

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countries and working in different sectors. The findings indicate that, although family issues—such as caring for children and household tasks—influence the choice to become entrepreneurs, the main drivers are personal fulfillment, the search for financial independence, and the perception of opportunities. This suggests that in the region, entrepreneurship tends to be more opportunity-driven than necessity-driven. The most frequently cited challenge was balancing household responsibilities with professional life.

Souza et al. (2024) examined how social support networks help women entrepreneurs in the food and beverage sector in Aracaju cope with the challenges at the intersection of work and family. Using a qualitative and exploratory approach, the study interviewed six businesswomen from Aracaju with a semi-structured guide. Narrative analysis of the data revealed conflicts between work and family spheres, and highlighted the importance of support networks, mainly formed by family members and colleagues. Although these networks play an essential role, they do not eliminate conflicts but rather help to ease the burden in the entrepreneurs' routines.

RELISE published studies such as Cruz et al. (2019), which analyzed the benefits of the Confeita+ Limeira project that trains low-income women in sustainable baking and entrepreneurship. Through a case study and questionnaires with participants and organizers, the study found that the project improves both technical qualifications and entrepreneurial skills such as leadership and innovation. The results underscore the importance of social projects for women's empowerment and offer insights for improving and expanding similar initiatives.

Nogueira (2019) analyzed the emancipatory potential of female entrepreneurship through the biographical narrative of Noémia, a Portuguese woman who became a business owner in a traditionally male sector. By exploring her journey, the research reveals the deep meaning of her entrepreneurial action,

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challenging the simplistic association of entrepreneurship with women's emancipation. While recognizing the role of the Welfare State as a promoter of this process, the study concludes that female emancipation remains limited by gender inequalities and the fragility of state programs, highlighting persistent structural challenges.

Barbosa (2019) analyzed the profile, challenges, and achievements of eight women entrepreneurs in the central hinterland of Ceará, with interviews conducted in Quixadá and Quixeramobim. The results show great diversity in ages, with most being married and having children. The main motivations included passion for work, while challenges involved economic crises, lack of capital, and gender-related barriers. The main achievements were recognition, independence, and the fulfillment of dreams, reinforcing the female presence in a traditionally male domain.

Maia, Giolda, and Maia (2019) investigated whether rural managers possess entrepreneurial traits and what those traits are. Using a qualitative, exploratory approach, six women involved in rural productive activities were interviewed. Results indicate that these women are motivated by business continuity and improved living conditions. The main challenges include lack of resources and investment. Entrepreneurial characteristics such as persistence, information-seeking, skills development, and networking were highlighted.

Silva (2020) analyzed the reasons that led women in Belo Horizonte to start their businesses. Through a qualitative approach, 11 entrepreneurs with more than one year of experience were interviewed. The results indicate that these women became entrepreneurs due to necessity and face challenges such as financial barriers and lack of access to information. Despite difficulties, common characteristics stood out, such as resilience and personal and professional recognition.

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Costa (2021) explored the influence of education, business activity, and cultural acceptance on women's entrepreneurial initiatives. Using a quantitative approach, involving 1,672 respondents from 49 countries, multiple linear regression analysis revealed that while formal education supports female entrepreneurship, cultural acceptance plays a more significant role. The results highlight the importance of social attitudes in encouraging female entrepreneurship.

The study analyzes the growth of female participation in entrepreneurship, still largely dominated by men. Based on academic literature and data from the GEM report, it concludes that male hegemony in the market is due to social barriers and specific difficulties faced by women. Recognizing the management skills of women is essential to overcoming these obstacles, but significant change requires broad social support.

Senff, Franco, and Schmidmeier (2021) analyzed the challenges faced by women entrepreneurs in Mafra (SC) in balancing personal and professional life. Through qualitative research and semi-structured interviews, the study found that schedule flexibility is crucial for balancing work and family. Support from family members and partners and a sense of personal achievement help overcome challenges. The study also points out that the business sector influences this dynamic, suggesting that analyses of work-life balance should consider this variable.

Teixeira (2021) researched the growth of women in entrepreneurship: although female participation in the entrepreneurial market is increasing, this sector is still largely dominated by men. The research sought to understand why, despite satisfactory quality in female management and its contribution to women's inclusion, male dominance persists. The analysis of articles, books, theses, and GEM data reveals that various factors explain this inequality, including social difficulties and gender barriers. Recognizing women's potential

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to manage and lead is crucial to overcoming these obstacles, but significant changes require support from society as a whole.

Richter (2022) identified the challenges faced by Generation Y women entrepreneurs in Caxias do Sul. Through an exploratory, qualitative approach, ten women entrepreneurs were interviewed. The main challenges identified were gaining market space, retaining customers, managing the business, defining working hours, and developing self-confidence. The results broaden the understanding of current behavior among both women entrepreneurs and Generation Y consumers.

Ferreira and Krakauer (2022) built on the research of Meneses and Krakauer (2019), which investigated the lack of persistence among Brazilian women entrepreneurs. The goal was to analyze the behavioral profile of women startup founders to see if low persistence was found in this group as well. The exploratory, qualitative research used the M.A.R.E.® diagnosis (Coda, 2016). Results indicate that startup founders, like other women entrepreneurs, have little analytical orientation, reflecting a low level of persistence. The study contributes to projects that promote self-knowledge and the strengthening of women-led businesses.

Santos (2023) investigated the motivations, challenges, and perspectives of six micro-entrepreneurs from Aracaju in this sector, using an exploratory, qualitative approach with semi-structured interviews. Results show that financial, personal, and market factors motivated these women to start online businesses. Main challenges include sector competition, lack of training, knowledge, and confidence—both from clients and themselves. Despite these difficulties, the entrepreneurs showed optimism about the future of their businesses.

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FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Female entrepreneurship has increasingly stood out and, consequently, has become a subject of research in the academic field. As presented in this study, most published articles focus on deciphering the motivations behind this phenomenon.

It was noted that the majority of the studies analyzed in this article are related to case studies and interviews that sought to understand the reasons women choose to become entrepreneurs, also highlighting the overload faced by women who divide their entrepreneurial activities with household tasks.

Analyzing these results, it was observed that the number of publications on the topic of female entrepreneurship and women entrepreneurs has grown. However, the amount is still limited when compared to the number of articles published on other, more general topics related to entrepreneurship, which presents an opportunity for further contributions on women's entrepreneurship.

Furthermore, studies like this, which aim to provide an overview of the scientific research on a particular topic, help to understand the current state of the art and can suggest directions for future researchers to delve deeper and advance knowledge in the area.

As with any research, methodological and operational limitations are present: only Brazilian journals with a certain Capes classification were investigated, a decision made due to accessibility to the database. Such limitation leads to the suggestion of future studies that encompass a greater number of journals and even a bibliometric study that could bring new insights into the state of the art on this subject.

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